

THE ROLE OF TALENT MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE ACEH GOVERNMENT

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Abstract:

The purpose of this study is to find out empirically the relationship between the influence of exogenous variables on endogenous variables, and to know the role of intervening variables, where the performance of employees to be studied is the performance of civil servants who work in the public sector (non-profit), so that Aceh government institutions and agencies are considered quite representative with this research setting. The subjects of this study were employees at 47 offices/agencies in Aceh Province with a sample of 337 people using convenience sampling technique, while the data were analyzed using Pearson correlation. The data analysis method in this study was used to test and explain the causal relationship between research variables shown in a series of path analysis models. The results of the analysis specifically obtained that the influence of intellectual capital on organizational performance proved to have a positive and significant relationship. The results of the respondent's assessment of the talent management variable (Y) on employee performance in the sufficient category is 3.30.

Keywords: Professional Competence, Employee Involvement, Sharing Leadership, Talent Management, Soft Skills and Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

Improving the quality of employee resources is very urgent and needs to be carried out in a planned, directed, and sustainable manner in order to improve capabilities and professionalism. The target of developing the quality of employee resources is to improve the operational performance of employees in carrying out government tasks. In addition, the high quality of employee resources will lead to the birth of a strong commitment in completing routine tasks according to their respective responsibilities and functions more efficiently, effectively, and productively. Talent management is a challenge for all organizations because the competition for certain positions is too tight (Al Ariss, et al, 2014). The talent shortage has become a dilemma for almost all organizations. This is because the skills possessed by available workers do not match those of more advanced and more complex skills. Most studies in the field of human resources, propose that organizations should ensure that they have a plan in place to meet the problem of talent shortages especially in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0

(Festing, M., & Schäfer, L. 2014). Talent shortage is a serious matter for the future growth of the organization.

One aspect that is considered to have a major influence in the sustainability of this bureaucratic reform process is the aspect of the State Civil Apparatus. The level of competence of the State Civil Apparatus is not optimal yet in the ranks of the bureaucracy, menjadi salah satu hal yang dianggap menghambat pencapaian tujuan reformasi. Major interference in the career policy of an apparatus, resulting in the competence and performance of civil servants are often defeated by the political ability to always be close to policy makers. As a result, basic services, which are mandatory affairs of local governments, are managed by officials who lack competence which also has a direct impact on the low performance and quality of public services. The results Ombudsman survey of the Republic Indonesia in 2016 showed that only 13 provinces out of 33 provinces, 16 cities out of 55 cities and 15 districts out of 85 surveyed districts received green (good) scores..

The low performance of the bureaucracy (State Civil Apparatus) results in the low quality of public services, even resulting in service users having to pay high costs (high cost economy). The bad picture of the bureaucracy (low performance of State Civil Apparatus Employees) is due to the lack or even incompetence of some structural officials and staff within the state apparatus. To realize this professional and highly competent human resources, among others, it is shown by the importance of career development for State Civil Apparatus Officers which is carried out on the basis of a combination of work performance and career systems. For this reason, the development of State Civil Apparatus Employees is based on professional competence, talent management and other supporting variables is a must, so that the organization (bureaucracy) can realize better performance and provide excellent public services.

Provisions regarding the quality of public services, especially the Aceh Province, have been regulated in Qanun No. 8 of 2008 concerning Public Services. Where in the Qanun Article 2 it is explained that the implementation of public services in Aceh Province is carried out in accordance with general principles, namely Islamic, justice, humanity, government administration, legal certainty, proportionality, equality, openness, participatory, accountability, public interest, professionalism, equal rights, balance of rights and obligations, efficiency, effectiveness, sustainability and gender sensitivity. And in Article 16 it is explained that public services in Aceh Province are based on the principles of simplicity, clarity, certainty, accuracy, non-discrimination, responsibility, honesty, completeness of facilities and infrastructure, ease of access, not receiving compensation in any form, accuracy, discipline, morality, security, order and comfort (Qanun No. 8, 2008).

Table.1. Results of Evaluation of Accountability Reports and Performance of Government Agencies

No	Province	Provincial AKIP Score	Predicate *	City Average	Predicate **
1	Aceh	60,25	B	48,19	C
2	Sumatera Utara	55,33	CC	46,19	C
3	Sumatera Barat	72,92	BB	57,17	CC
4	Riau	66,50	B	56,53	CC
5	Kep. Riau	70,13	BB	63,07	B
6	Jambi	58,70	CC	58,59	CC
7	Sumatera Selatan	80,01	A	55,87	CC
8	Kep. Bangka Belitung	63,65	B	60,90	B
9	Bengkulu	64,67	B	45,83	C
10	Banten	55,90	CC	62,28	B
11	Jawa Barat	80,96	A	61,31	B
12	Bali	76,73	BB	64,92	B
13	Jawa Timur	81,21	A	64,19	B
14	Kalimantan Barat	63,13	B	52,26	CC
15	Kalimantan Selatan	77,29	BB	59,65	CC
16	Kalimantan Tengah	61,35	B	51,22	CC
17	Kalimantan Timur	77,50	BB	58,09	CC
18	Kalimantan Utara	60,05	B	49,30	C
19	Lampung	61,63	B	51,32	CC
20	Nusa Tenggara Barat	61,01	B	56,13	CC
21	Nusa Tenggara Timur	63,75	B	47,84	C
22	DKI Jakarta	65,06	B	-	-
23	DI Yogyakarta	84,22	A	74,28	BB
24	Jawa Tengah	75,94	BB	57,66	CC
No	Province	Provincial AKIP Score	Predicate *	City Average	Predicate **
25	Sulawesi Utara	62,63	B	53,03	CC
26	Gorontalo	60,21	B	61,66	B
27	Sulawesi Tengah	-	-	50,52	CC
28	Sulawesi Barat	-	-	43,26	C
29	Sulawesi Selatan	-	-	50,54	CC
30	Sulawesi Tenggara	-	-	44,60	C
31	Maluku Utara	-	-	28,75	D
32	Maluku	-	-	47,25	C
33	Papua	-	-	20,51	D
34	Papua Barat	-	-	38,79	C
Information: Predicate* (is a column that shows the predicate of the Provincial AKIP value in LETTERS) Predicate** (is a column that shows the predicate of AKIP scores. Average district/city in each province in LETTERS, for example, Aceh province has 23 districts/cities, West Java has 27 districts/cities and so on, then this column shows the average AKIP value each district/city in LETTERS) AA = (90-100); A = (80-90); BB = (70-80); B = (60-70); CC = (50-60); C = (30-50); D = (0-30)					

Source: Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Reform (2020)

This is in accordance with the results of the Performance Accountability System for Government Agencies published by the Ministry of Empowerment of State Apparatus and Bureaucratic Reform in 2020, where the performance of Aceh Province public services for 2019 received a report card with a P³ value, while for the average value of public services at

the district/city level in Aceh Province, the report card score is P⁴. Report from the Ministry of Administrative Reform and Bureaucratic Empowerment (2020), for 2019 Aceh Province received the title of SAKIP P³ (effective enough), while for the performance of district/city governments in Aceh Province, the SAKIP score is still in the P⁴ (effective) predicate. While the winners of the highest SAKIP scores for 2019 were won by Central Sulawesi Province, DI Yogyakarta and Lahat Regency with the highest score, namely P⁵ (very effective).

The evaluation of SAKIP is based on 6 aspects and 6 principles of public service, namely aspects of service policy, professionalism of Human Resources, infrastructure, consultation and complaints, innovation, and is guided by the principles of justice, participation, accountability, transparency, efficiency, accessibility. Of the 6 aspects and 6 principles that determine the quality of public services, the role of Human Resources is very important. Service performance from local governments can only be achieved if the government has Human Resources who have good performance, which ultimately can provide maximum service quality to the community.

Achievement of the performance of government agencies is largely determined from the performance of employees who work within the organization. So far, it is difficult to assess whether an employee has had a good performance or not, as it can be seen that there are obstacles in evaluating the performance of employees working in agencies in Aceh Province, this happens because there are no standard provisions regarding performance appraisal indicators. The researcher conducted an initial interview with the Aceh Civil Service Agency to ask what the main obstacles were in assessing the performance of ASN in Aceh Province. From the results of the interview, information was obtained that performance appraisal was only carried out with reference to 2 performance indicators, namely absenteeism (60%) and supervisor's assessment (40%), and seem non-objective. However, as of January 1, 2020, there are official guidelines from the government with the ratification of Government Regulation (PP) Number 30 of 2019 concerning the Performance Assessment of Civil Servants, where the Performance Assessment is carried out based on a Civil Service Performance Management System consisting of (1) performance planning; (2) implementation, performance monitoring, and performance coaching; (3) performance appraisal; (4) follow-up; and (5) Civil Service Performance Information System.

Another phenomenon that the researchers succeeded in revealing from the results of initial interviews with the Aceh Personnel Board is that there is currently a "complaint" feature on the performance appraisal application system that can be used by employees to complain about unfair performance appraisals carried out by superiors. For example, the superior (echelon 3) gives a score of 60 to the employee's performance, while the employee who is assessed feels that the value should be 80. For things like this, employees can directly write down their criticisms and complaints, so that echelon 2 superiors can respond directly to the employee's complaints. Another problem related to performance appraisal in Aceh Province is that there are no definite indicators in managing talent tools in government organizations in Aceh.

The supporting factor for the success of employee performance is employee involvement. The importance of the concept of talent management for organizations has been proven through

research conducted by Hughes and Rog (2008), which the results of his research reveal that human resources are the main source of organizational competitive advantage, and the implementation of talent management programs implemented by the organization has been proven to be effective in increasing employee retention rates by increasing employee engagement.

Talent management in other studies is also strongly influenced by the level of employee engagement shown through employee commitment to the organization (Mohammad, 2015). Employees who are involved in the organization will feel passionate about work and have high dedication to the organization, so talent management programs such as employee development and training will be more effective for employees who have involvement in the organization.

Furthermore, the factor that influences the success of employee performance in the Aceh government is shared leadership. In research conducted by Pearce et al., (2009) which states that employee performance is largely determined by the shared leadership role that is applied in an organization. Furthermore, the role of leadership in talent management practice is to ensure organizational commitment to employees based on the belief that employees are the main source of organizational competitive advantage which is an important organizational asset that must be developed (knowledge and skills) and maintained (Hughes and Rog, 2008; Pearce et al., 2009).

Factors supporting the success of employee performance cannot be separated from the potential of employee Soft Skills, namely as a quality needed by workers that is not related to technical knowledge only but with the ability to interact with others and the ability to adapt. Purnami (2013) describes soft skills as being so important because many agencies or organizations not only need smart workers who are able to do the tasks given. Agencies now also want workers (employees) who are able to communicate, sociable, hardworking, intelligent, adaptable to the work environment, and have the ability to work together with colleagues and superiors.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Professional Competence

The origin of the competence of Civil Servants can be traced to the vision of bureaucratic reform as outlined in Presidential Regulation 81/2010, namely “The Realization of World Class Government”, namely a professional and high-integrity government that is able to provide excellent service to the community. Article 4 paragraph (1) Presidential Regulation 81/2010 states that “The operational implementation of the grand design of bureaucratic reform 2010-2025 will be outlined in the bureaucratic reform road map which is set every five years by the Minister of Empowerment of State Apparatus Bureaucratic Reform. Rocha et.al (2017) explained that professional competence is an advantage that a person has where these advantages are not only related to work but also have a positive effect on behavior and improve one's performance. Epstein and Hundert (2002) divide the professional competence of employees into 7 indicators, namely basic abilities, procedural skills, dealing with uncertainty, time use, communication skills, emotional intelligence, and willingness to correct mistakes.

2. Employee Engagement

Organizations need employees with high involvement to be able to work diligently for the betterment of the organization. The importance of employee involvement as an intangible company asset. Ferizal (2016) describes employee involvement as the desire and ability of employees to contribute to the success of the organization by devoting all their abilities, energy, thoughts, and more time. Ferizal (2016) adds that employee involvement is a process for someone to be involved (involve), enthusiastic (enthusiast), have commitment and give more effort for the company or organization where you work. Azoury et. al, (2014) asserted that employee engagement is a combination of emotional and intellectual involvement that motivates employees to do their best in their work. Rahmi and Mulyadi (2018) state that there are 4 (four) indicators of employee involvement in an agency, namely: (1) Work participation, (2) Organizational success, (3) Achievement of goals, and (4) The success of an organization/company.

3. Sharing Leadership

The emergence of the concept of shared leadership is in contrast to the concept of dual positions in traditional organizations, where sharing leadership allows the delegation of leadership authority to organizational members / employees to decide a problem, take the initiative and make decisions. Hoch and Dulebohn (2013) explain that shared leadership is a collective leadership run by team members characterized by collaborative decision-making and shared responsibility for achieving the desired results. Sharing leadership requires distributing responsibilities and leadership roles to different team members (Carson, Tesluk, & Marrone, 2007). Sharing leadership focuses on interactions between team members, rather than interactions between formally appointed leaders and their subordinates (Muethel and Hoegl, 2013). Therefore, sharing leadership can create conditions in which leaders can adapt to situations quickly and flexibly, respond to what is really happening and resolve organizational problems quickly. Hiler (2002) divides the dimensions of shared leadership based on the indicators: (1) Planning how to get the job done, (2) Allocate team resources according to team priorities, (3) Find solutions to problems that affect team performance, (4) Utilize team experts to solve problems, (5) Provide support to team members who need help, (6) Listening to complaints and problems from team members, (7) Helping to develop the abilities of each team member, and (8) Providing direction to team members who are underperforming how to improve their performance.

4. Soft Skills

Aribowo (2008) suggests that: “Soft Skill is a person's skill in dealing with other people (including with himself). Haselberger, et.al, (2012) in Shaffie (2016) said that the current world of work requires prospective employees to have soft skills as an important factor that determines work ability in various fields. However, the provision of soft skills is still very rare and only around 10% in the world of education. The position of soft skills is only an additional aspect, even though soft skill A good attitude is needed to improve the career and

professionalism of employees (John, 2009; Singh & Jaykumar, 2019; Ariwibowo, et.al, 2020). Ariwibowo, et.al (2020) suggested 11 indicators of Soft Skills, namely: (1) Self-discipline, (2) Responsible, (3) Enthusiastic in carrying out work, (4) Ability to solve problems, (5) Able to collaborate with others. (6) Able to speak well. (7) Pleasant personality. (8) Social behavior, (9) Thinking critically, (10) Thinking creatively and innovatively, and (11) Confident and self-motivated. In addition, the Soft Skill indicators according to Robbins translated by Benjamin Molan (2014) are (1) Self-awareness, (2) Self-management, (3) Self-motivation, (3) Empathy, and (4) Social skills.

5. Talent Management

Talent management has become the “key” of management in recent years. This was driven by research in 1990, by a group of Mc Kinsey consultants who coined the term "The War For Talent" to describe the important role of employees in determining the success of an organization (Scullion et al, 2010) stated talented people are those who do the following: regularly demonstrate extraordinary abilities and excel well through various activities and situations, or possess special skills that consistently demonstrate high competence. In addition, Ernie & Ratri (2016: 3) describe talent as an employee who is able to contribute above average through achieving high performance and ownership of potential that will affect the current and future growth of the organization. According to Sweem (2009) talent management has 8 indicators, namely: (1) Providing new ideas and giving recognition to these ideas, (2) Feedback on performance directly, (3) Discuss future opportunities, (4) Opportunities for career development, (5) Rewards and recognition are always given to performance, (6) There is a very clear link between performance and salary, (7) Assign responsibilities, and (8) Organization supports and provides resources needed for career development.

6. Employee Performance

Robbins (2008) defines performance as a result achieved by employees in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a job. According to Mensah and Tawiah (2016), employee performance is seen as a form of employee's positive contribution to organizational performance. Meanwhile, in general, employee performance is defined as an individual's ability to achieve work goals and targets in accordance with the expectations set by the organization (Maathis and Jackson, quoted in Mensah, 2016). Ghani et al., (2016) interpret employee performance as employee knowledge and skills that are able to guide employees to carry out various organizational activities. Osman et al., (2016) added that employee performance is the ability of employees to complete their duties and have behavior that is in accordance with organizational norms and culture. In the research of Osman et al., (2016) employee performance is measured using non-financial indicators namely ability, motivation, self-discipline and cooperation. So it can be understood that employee performance is employee performance achieved through increasing employee abilities/skills that can have an impact on improving organizational performance. Indicators used to measure employee performance at least according to John Miner in Sudarmanto (2009), are: (1) Work Quantity, namely the amount of work produced by employees such as the number of activities or the number of tasks carried out in accordance with the specified time, (2) Work Quality, namely

the level and extent to which the results of the activities carried out by work employees are reviewed from the level of error, accuracy, (3) the use of time in work (timeliness).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This type of research is confirmatory with a survey method. Data collection was carried out using a questionnaire on 47 offices/agencies in Aceh Province. Sampling technique using convenience sampling. The data will be tested for validity using Pearson correlation where the questionnaire data is said to be valid if the Pearson correlation value $> r$ table (0.227), while reliability testing uses Cronbach's Alpha ($CR > 0.70$). The data analysis method used multiple regression (t-test and F-test).

Figure 1: Research Model

The questionnaire used to collect data is using a Likert Scale Summated Rating with an interval measuring scale (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). The Likert scale is designed to test how strongly the respondents agree or disagree with the given statement (Sekaran & Bougie, 2013). The criteria for determining the alternative weights of respondents' answer choices are:

Table 1: Alternative Answer Options Based on Scale or Weight

Alternative Answer Options	Scale or Weight
Strongly disagree	1
Don't agree	2
Disagree	3
Agree	4
Strongly agree	5

The variables of this study consisted of six variables, namely three independent variables (exogenous), namely the Professional Competence Variable (X1), Employee Involvement (X2) and Sharing Leadership (X3). One Talent Management Variable (Y) which acts as an intervening variable, and one Soft Skills variable (M) as a moderating variable. As for acting

as the dependent variable (endogenous) is Employee Performance (Z). If there are items that do not meet the requirements, then the item will not be investigated further. The conditions that must meet the criteria according to Sugiyono (2016) are as follows::

- a. If $r \geq 0.30$, then the items are declared valid
- b. If $r \leq 0,30$ then the items are declared invalid

Test the validity of the instrument can use the correlation formula. The correlation formula based on Pearson Product Moment (Arikunto, 2013) is as follows:

$$r_{xy} = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{\{n\sum X^2 - (\sum X)^2\}\{n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2\}}}$$

The basis for making decisions in reliability testing is as follows:

- a. a. If Cronbach's Alpha value > 0.60 then the questionnaire is declared reliable or consistent.
- b. b. If Cronbach's Alpha value < 0.60 then the questionnaire is declared unreliable or inconsistent.

To determine the variance of each item, the following Riduwan (2009) formula is used: $S_i =$

$\frac{\sum X_i^2 - \frac{(\sum x_i)^2}{N}}{N}$ Furthermore, to calculate the reliability of the instrument on the Y variable using the Alpha Cronbach formula, namely:

$$r_{11} = \left[\frac{k}{k-1} \right] \left[1 - \frac{\sum S_i}{S_t} \right]$$

To assess the achievement of the quality of work of employees, can use the guidelines set out in the Regulation of the Head of the State Civil Service Agency Number 1 of 2013, as follows:

Table 2: Indicators of Assessment of Employee Work Quality Achievements

Value Criteria	Information
91 - 100	The work is perfect, and the above service has no errors, no revisions, determined standards and others.
76 -90	The work results have I (one) or 2 (two) minor errors, no major errors, revisions, and services according to predetermined standards and others.
61 - 75	The work results have 3 (three) or 4 (four) minor errors, and there are no major errors, revisions, and services are sufficient to meet the specified standards and others.
51 60	The results of the work have 5 (five) minor errors and there are major errors, revisions, and services that do not meet the specified standards and others.
≤ 50	The results of the work have more than 5 (five) minor errors and there are major errors, unsatisfactoriness, revisions, service below the specified standards and others.

Source: PERKA State Finance Agency No. 1 Year 2013

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIO

From the primary data and the results of the questionnaire, the respondents' demographic data were obtained as follows:

- **Characteristics by gender**

Table 3: Number and Percentage of Respondents by Gender

No	Gender	Amount (person)	Percentage
1	Man	226	67,06%
2	Woman	111	32,94
Total		337	100%

Source: processed primary data, 2022

Based on the data in Table 3 regarding the distribution of the sexes of the respondents, this study shows that there are 226 male respondents (67.06%) of the total number of respondents. Meanwhile, there were 111 female respondents (32.94%) of the total number of respondents. In this case, the research respondents are dominated by men.

- **Characteristics By Age**

Table 4: Number and Percentage of Respondents by Age

No	Age Group	Amount (person) Man	Jumlah (orang) Woman	Percentage
1	20-24 tahun	19	10	13,63%
2	25-29 tahun	54	34	25,10%
3	30-34 tahun	88	-	25,10%
4	35-39 tahun	41	47	24,12%
5	≥40	24	20	12,05%
Total		226	111	100%

Source: processed primary data, 2022Based on the data in Table 4 regarding the age distribution of respondents, this study shows that there are 29 respondents in the 20-30 years age range (13.63%), the age range of 25-29 years as many as 88 people (25.10%), the age range of 30-34 years is 88 people (25.10%), the age range of 35-39 years is 88 people (24.12%) and respondents with an age range of more than 40 years are 44 people (12.05%) of the total respondents. The data above shows that respondents aged between 25-29 years and 30-34 years dominate the age range compared to others.

- **Characteristics Based on Last Education**

Table 5: Number and Percentage of Respondents Based on Last Education

No	Statement	Amount (person)	Percentage
1	Diploma	37	10,98%
2	Bachelor	203	60,24%
3	Master (S2)	95	28,18%
4	Doctor (S3)	2	0,60%
Total		337	100%

Source: processed primary data, 2022

Based on the data in Table 5 regarding the distribution of the number of respondents' last education level, this study shows that there are 37 respondents with Diploma background (10.98%), 203 undergraduates (60.24%), Masters as many as 95 people (28.18%) and Doctors as many as 2 people (0.6%) of the total number of respondents. So from these data it shows that respondents with educational backgrounds. Bachelors are more dominant than respondents with other educational backgrounds.

Table 6. Respondents' Assessment Results on Talent Management Variable (Y) on Employee Performance

No	Statement	Answer					Total Score	Average Score	Rating Category
		STS	IS	RR	S	S			
1	My department always encourages and appreciates new ideas from employees	0	40	75	87	135	1078	3,19	Enough
2	The leader always gives feedback on my work	3	56	78	94	106	1039	3,08	Enough
3	The leadership wants to discuss about my future career opportunities	0	34	81	96	126	1099	3,26	Enough
4	I feel I have the opportunity to develop a career in the future	5	32	84	93	123	1091	3,24	Enough
5	I get awards and recognition for every performance that I give	0	37	82	96	122	1022	3,03	Cukup
6	I feel that the salary I receive today is in accordance with my workload	10	32	84	93	118	1040	3,08	enough
7	Leaders often delegate organizational responsibilities/tasks to me	0	23	94	99	121	1079	3,20	enough
8	The organization always supports and provides convenience in my career development	2	32	87	96	120	1190	3,53	Well
Amount							8906	26,42	enough
Average Score							1113,2	3,30	

Source: processed data, 2022

Table 6 explains respondents' perceptions of talent management variables seen from the eighth statement "The organization always supports and provides convenience in my career development" has the highest average score of 3.53 percent. Meanwhile, from the fifth statement "I get awards and recognition for every performance achievement that I give", has the lowest average score of 3.03 percent. The average total value of respondents' answers is 3.30 in the sufficient category, then this means that overall employees give a less positive response to the talent management variable.

- The following are the results of the reliability test of each variable

Table 7. Summary of reliability test results as follows:

No	Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
1	Penilaian terhadap variabel Kompetensi Profesional (X1)	0.714	Reliable
2	Penilaian terhadap variabel Keterlibatan Pegawai (X2)	0.820	Reliable
3	Penilaian terhadap variabel Kepemimpinan Berbagi (X3)	0.709	Reliable
4	Penilaian terhadap variabel Soft Skills (M)	0.723	Reliable
5	Penilaian terhadap variabel Manajemen Bakat (Y)	0.789	Reliable
6	Penilaian terhadap variabel Kinerja Pegawai (Z)	0.814	Reliable

Sumber: data primer yang telah diolah, 2022

Based on Table 7, it shows that the Cronbach's Alpha value of each variable is more than 0.70. This shows that the statement items from the questionnaire are reliable and each statement item used is able to obtain consistent data. If the statement is resubmitted, it will get an answer that is relatively the same as the previous answer.

III. CONCLUSIONE

employee performance in Aceh government employees is influenced by the direct role of professional competence, employee involvement, leadership sharing, talent management and the indirect role of soft skills as a mediator on organizational performance. However, the role of soft skills has the most crucial role in the relationship of influence between professional competence, employee involvement, leadership sharing, talent management on employee performance, where if there is no soft skill role as a mediator then this direct relationship will not be meaningful. With the superior talent management owned by Aceh government agencies, it is expected to be able to boost employee performance, and make Aceh government agencies a form of productive and effective governance of the State Civil Apparatus at the Aceh provincial level.

The results of this study indicate the large role of professional competence, employee involvement, leadership sharing, talent management and soft skills in achieving optimal employee performance. Therefore, the policy implications recommended for Aceh government agencies are (1) to concentrate on increasing staff resources, by providing various skills training, and implementing a reward system for outstanding employees, (2) Realizing and affirming a religious government organizational culture as a basis for behavior and identity for employees, and (3) provide comparative studies to employees who excel in order to increase the repertoire of thinking as well as become agency ambassadors in moving their work programs, and as a form of participation in building relationships between agencies.

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